

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Production performance of Holstein cows at 4 stages of lactation fed 4 dietary crude protein concentrations

P. Letelier, G. I. Zanton, and M. A. Wattiaux

Supplementary Table S2. Predicted range in dietary CP for which there was no difference in production responses with increasing DIM¹

DIM	Dietary CP range, % CP	Predicted responses
	DMI, kg/d	
120	16.3 – 17.4 – (18.5)	31.5 – 32.4 – (31.1)
130	16.3 – 17.4 – (18.5)	31.3 – 32.1 – (30.9)
140	16.4 – 17.5 – (18.5)	31.1 – 31.9 – (30.7)
150	16.4 – 17.5 – (18.6)	30.9 – 31.7 – (30.6)
160	16.4 – 17.5 – (18.6)	30.8 – 31.5 – (30.5)
170	16.4 – 17.5 – (18.6)	30.7 – 31.4 – (30.3)
180	16.5 – 17.5 – (18.6)	30.6 – 31.3 – (30.2)
190	16.4 – 17.5 – (18.6)	30.5 – 31.2 – (30.1)
200	16.4 – 17.5 – (18.6)	30.3 – 31.0 – (29.9)
210	16.3 – 17.5 – (18.6)	30.2 – 30.9 – (29.8)
220	16.3 – 17.4 – (18.6)	30.0 – 30.8 – (29.6)
230	16.2 – 17.4 – (18.6)	29.8 – 30.6 – (29.4)
240	16.1 – 17.3 – (18.5)	29.6 – 30.4 – (29.1)
250	16.0 – 17.2 – (18.5)	29.4 – 30.2 – (28.8)
260	15.8 – 17.1 – (18.4)	29.2 – 30.0 – (28.5)
270	15.7 – 17.1 – (18.4)	28.9 – 29.7 – (28.2)
	Milk NE _L output ² , Mcal/d	
120	16.2 – 17.3 – (18.4)	35.0 – 36.3 – (34.3)
130	16.3 – 17.3 – (18.4)	34.4 – 35.7 – (33.7)
140	16.3 – 17.4 – (18.4)	33.8 – 35.0 – (33.1)
150	16.3 – 17.4 – (18.5)	33.2 – 34.4 – (32.6)
160	16.3 – 17.4 – (18.5)	32.6 – 33.8 – (32.0)
170	16.3 – 17.4 – (18.5)	32.1 – 33.2 – (31.4)
180	16.3 – 17.4 – (18.5)	31.5 – 32.6 – (30.8)
190	16.3 – 17.4 – (18.5)	30.9 – 32.0 – (30.2)
200	16.2 – 17.4 – (18.5)	30.3 – 31.4 – (29.5)
210	16.2 – 17.3 – (18.5)	29.6 – 30.8 – (28.8)
220	16.1 – 17.3 – (18.5)	28.9 – 30.1 – (28.0)
230	16.0 – 17.2 – (18.4)	28.1 – 29.3 – (27.1)
240	15.9 – 17.1 – (18.4)	27.3 – 28.5 – (26.2)
250	15.8 – 17.1 – (18.4)	26.4 – 27.7 – (25.2)
260	15.6 – 17.0 – 18.3	25.5 – 26.8 – 24.1
270	15.5 – 16.9 – 18.3	24.5 – 25.8 – 23.0

¹The ranges were determined by calculating the dietary CP% at the maximum predicted response (i.e., middle value), and the dietary CP at lower and upper 95% confidence interval limits of the maximum predicted response (i.e., left, and right values). Values between parenthesis indicate that the confidence limit was outside the dietary CP range fed in this study, thus the values presented showed the limits within the data

²Milk net energy output calculated according to NRC (2001).